

Bismuth nitrate-induced microwave-mediated deglycosylation of O-glycosides: Synthesis of enantiopure 3-hydroxy β -lactams

Indrani Banik^a, Ram Naresh Yadav^b, Fredrick F. Becker^a and Bimal Krishna Banik^{a,b,c,d*}

^aDepartment of Molecular Pathology, The University of Texas-M. D. Anderson Cancer Centre, 1515 Holcombe Blvd., Houston, Texas 77030, USA

^bDepartment of Chemistry, The University of Texas-Pan American, 1201 West University Drive, Edinburg, Texas 78539, USA

^cDepartment of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, Stevens Institute of Technology, Castle Point on the Hudson, Hoboken, New Jersey 07030, USA

^dCurrent Address: Vice President of Research and Education Development, Community Health Systems of South Texas, 3135 South Sugar Road, Edinburg, Texas 78539, USA

E-mail: bimalbanik10@gmail.com, bimal.banik@chsst.org

Manuscript received 01 October 2018, accepted 02 November 2018

Bismuth nitrate-induced microwave-mediated cleavages of O-glycosidic bond in β -lactams are achieved to afford their corresponding hydroxyl derivatives in excellent yields.

Keywords: Bismuth nitrate, microwave, β -lactam, stereochemistry, optical activity.

Introduction

Due to the medicinal activities of numerous β -lactams, studies in these areas are highly desirable¹. Indeed since the discovery of penicillins as the life-saving drugs several thousand of papers have been published on β -lactams. Optically active β -lactams in both enantiomeric forms are difficult to obtain. Importantly, preparation of enantiopure β -lactams with two *cis* and two *trans* isomers remains the challenge. In this paper, we describe a simple method for the preparation of optically active two *cis* and two *trans* isomers via bismuth nitrate-induced microwave mediated O-glycosidic bond cleavage reaction. This method produces chiral 3-hydroxy β -lactams in optically active forms².

Background and significance:

Our research group demonstrated a few bismuth nitrate-pentahydrate-mediated novel reactions³. In some instances, these reactions were possible due to the coordination of an electronegative atom present in the reactants with bismuth that has a vacant d-orbital. In contrast, some reactions were successful as a result of liberated nitric acid in the reaction

Fig. 1. Optically active hydroxy/acetoxo β -lactams.

media. The two properties have made bismuth nitrate a unique reagent/catalyst in our research for the past many

years. It has also been found that reactions with bismuth nitrate are accelerated tremendously in a domestic or automated microwave oven. The advantages of microwave-induced reactions are proved through extensive series of investigations.

Results and discussion

Scheme 1. Enantioselective α -hydroxy- β -lactam via stereoselective O-glycosylation.

Entry	3(a-b)	4(a-b)	5(a-b)	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1	R ¹ = Ph R ² = Ph	R ¹ = Ph R ² = Ph	R ¹ = Ph R ² = Ph	6	80
2	R ¹ = Ph R ² = PMP	R ¹ = Ph R ² = PMP	R ¹ = Ph R ² = PMP	5	90

Some optically active hydroxy/acetoxyl β -lactams structures (1-12) are shown in Fig. 1. Stereospecific glycosylation of several hydroxy β -lactams with glycal derivatives through iodine-catalyzed method produced O-glycosides (Scheme 1). The 3,4-di-O-acetyl-L-rhamnal has been used as a glycosyl donor in presence of molecular iodine as promoter in dry THF as a solvent for this reaction. Both enantiomers of a *trans*-4-aryl-3-hydroxy-2-azetidinone glycosides **4a-b** and **5a-b** have been obtained via stereospecific glycosylation with rhamnal diacetate in presence of iodine (catalyst) (Scheme 1, Table 1)⁴.

We performed this glycosylation reaction in presence of indium metal as a promoter. Surprisingly, in all of the instances, the unsaturated O-glycosides were hydrogenated to saturated glycosides (Scheme 2, Table 2)⁵.

Scheme 2. Enantioselective α -hydroxy- β -lactam via stereoselective O-glycosylation unprecedented hydrogenolysis of unsaturated glycosides.

Table 2

Entry	3(a-b)	4(a-b)	5(a-b)	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1	R ¹ = Ph R ² = Ph	R ¹ = Ph R ² = Ph	R ¹ = Ph R ² = Ph	5	75
2	R ¹ = Ph R ² = PMP	R ¹ = Ph R ² = PMP	R ¹ = Ph R ² = PMP	6	80

After the successful synthesis of diverse *trans*-enantiomers of β -lactams, we turned our attention to synthesize the *cis*-enantiomers by using the *cis*-racemic β -lactams. The tri-O-acetyl-D-glucal has been used as glycosyl donor for stereospecific glycosylation (Scheme 3, Table 3).

Scheme 3. Stereospecific glycosylation with racemic *cis* 3-hydroxy β -lactam.

Table 3

Entry	9(a-b)	10(a-b)	11(a-b)	Time (h)	Yield (%)
1	R ¹ = Ph R ² = Ph	R ¹ = Ph R ² = Ph	R ¹ = Ph R ² = Ph	7	85
2	R ¹ = Ph R ² = PMP	R ¹ = Ph R ² = PMP	R ¹ = Ph R ² = PMP	8	90

The Ferrier glycosylation of polycyclic 3-hydroxy β -lactam failed to undergo reaction under this methodology. We synthesised the enantiopure β -lactams of polycyclic amine through Staudinger ketene-imine cycloaddition using sugar derived molecule (Scheme 4)⁶.

Scheme 4. Synthesis of optically active β -lactam of polycyclic aromatic amine.

Our next step was to remove the sugar moiety to obtain the enantiopure 3-hydroxy β -lactams for our ongoing research on anticancer β -lactams.

Initially we performed dilute hydrochloric acid-induced cleavage of glycosidic bond to remove the sugar group to obtain optically active β -hydroxy lactams in good yield. However, this deglycosylation method was slow since it was conducted at room temperature. To avoid corrosive hydrochloric acid, we performed the same reaction with bismuth nitrate-induced microwave-assisted method in aqueous tetrahydrofuran and the hydroxy products were obtained in good yields³.

Entry	Glycosides	Time (min)	Yield (%)	β -Lactam
1	4(a-b)	1–2	80.85	14(a-b)
2	5(a-b)	1–3	85.90	15(a-b)
3	6(a-b)	1–3	75.80	14(a-b)
4	7(a-b)	1–4	85.90	15(a-b)
5	10(a-b)	1–4	85.90	16(a-b)
6	11(a-b)	1–4	85.90	17(a-b)
7	13(a-b)	4–5	70.75	18(a-b)

These hydroxy compounds were then converted to their respective acetates with acetic anhydride in the presence of triethyl amine quantitatively.

Bismuth nitrate pentahydrate is extremely economical and stable nontoxic solid salts. This salt is highly compatible in microwave-assisted reaction conditions. The reactions are completed within 10–30 min with 20 mol% bismuth nitrate at medium power level of a domestic microwave oven. The temperature of the reaction mixture was controlled below 50° by

an on-off cycle present in the microwave oven. Higher amount of bismuth nitrate accelerates the reaction further. No nitration of the aromatic rings, deacetoxylation of the sugar units and hydrolysis of the β -lactam rings are observed under these conditions.

The β -lactams that have a single aromatic ring at the nitrogen undergoes deglycosylation faster than that β -lactams that have multicyclic aromatic rings at the nitrogen of the ring. In aqueous solution, bismuth nitrate liberates proton through the formation of nitric acid and thus a hydronium ion is formed. The ring oxygen of the glycoside (unsaturated or saturated) attacks the proton because it is more nucleophilic than the glycosidic oxygen (Scheme 4, A to B). The nucleophilicity of the glycosidic oxygen is reduced by the presence of the β -lactam ring. However, glycosidic oxygen is sufficiently nucleophilic to attack the protonated portion of the sugar (B to C). At the last step a second nucleophilic attack eliminates the sugar unit from the β -lactam ring leaving hydroxy β -lactam as the only product (C to D and E). The reaction does not take place in the absence of water.

Experimental

In a small microwave proof test tube, β -lactam glycosides (1 mmol) was taken with THF:water (1:1) (1 mL), and bismuth nitrate pentahydrate (0.5–1.0 mmol). The mixture was irradiated at 80°C for 1–5 min. The reaction mixture was diluted with dichloromethane (10 mL), washed with water (2 mL), organic part was dried with sodium sulfate and solvent was evaporated. The crude product showed identical IR and NMR data with the compounds prepared earlier by conventional methods. The purification of the compounds was carried out by column chromatography over silica gel bed with 50%–50% hexane and ethyl acetate as the eluents.

Scheme 5. Proposed scheme for deglycosylation.

Conclusion

A facile deglycosylation method in β -lactam chemistry is introduced with bismuth nitrate-induced reaction in a domestic microwave oven. The reaction is simple, environmentally benign and produces optically active products in both enantio-

meric forms with excellent yields. Some of the products or their derivatives described herein have potent anticancer activity against a variety of cancer cell lines.

Acknowledgement

BKB is grateful to NIH, NCI, Kleberg Foundation of Texas, Stevens Institute of Technology, University of Texas M. D. Anderson Cancer Centre, University of Texas Health Science Centre at San Antonio and University of Texas-Pan American for their support to our research.

References

1. Kamath and I. Ojima, *Tetrahedron*, 2012, **68**, 10640.
2. K. Banik, M. S. Manhas and A. K. Bose, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1994, **59**, 4714.
3. N. Srivastava and B. K. Banik, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2003, **68**, 2109.
4. K. Banik and M. S. Manhas, *Tetrahedron Symposium-in-print*, 2012, **68**, 10769.
5. S. Chandra, R. N. Yadav, A. Paniagua and B. K. Banik, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2016, **57**, 1425.
6. B. K. Banik, I. Banik and F. F. Becker, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **45**, 846.